

**STUDY ON WORK LIFE BALANCE AMONG YOUTH OF MUMBAI
WORKING IN CORPORATE SECTOR****Miss Yuvati Bharat Nandu***Assistant Professor**Mat. K. M. Patel Senior College of Commerce and Science***Abstract**

The term has three vital components – ‘work’, ‘life’ and ‘balance’. In simple terms, “work” is normally conceived of in this context as including paid employment while “life” includes activities outside work. The term ‘balance’ too, lends itself to a variety of meanings. A simplistic definition of balance may be “sufficient time to meet commitments at both home and work”

The demand for maintaining a work-life balance has risen unprecedentedly among the employees and the management has also acknowledged its importance in the current scenario. In future, work life balance will be one of the hot topics of debate in the boardrooms and is going to be a major area of concern for the management and HR professionals which they will be faced with.

With increasing stress levels and demands at the workplaces, attrition rate in organization is increasing. Therefore, the present day organizations are required to create a flexible environment which would help employees to manage their work and family together. This paper brings forth such issues and practices prevailing among youth working especially for corporate companies.

Keywords: Youth, Work life balance, working hours, Personal Life, Family

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Introduction

Defining work-life balance involves looking at how working people manage time spent at and outside of work. Time outside of work may include managing relationships, family responsibilities, and other outside interests and hobbies. The methods an individual uses to juggle all their work and life demands constitute their work-life balance. The definition is simple, yet working professionals everywhere struggle to define it for themselves, let alone achieve it. Those in pursuit find a complicated landscape with thousands of articles and claims to getting there. With many people feeling stressed and not “balanced” it’s time to take a look at how we conceptualize work-life balance and the ways in which it will need to evolve for professionals today.

Work and personal life were once considered to be two separate priorities. But with the changing times due to globalization and ever-increasing work pressures, maintaining work-life balance has attracted the attention of the organizations and employees as well. The employees, who devote a crucial period of time of their entire day at work or sometimes work for extended hours, are faced with the challenge of balancing their personal lives with the demands of their profession.

Objective of the Study

1. To study about the work life balance among youth working in corporate.
2. To analyze the difference among the work life balance of employees working 5 days a week and 6 days a week.
3. To study the impact of long working hours on personal lives.
4. To understand the problems faced by employees in managing work and personal life.

Scope of the Study

This research will be helpful to the various business organizations in framing the policies for improving / managing work life of their employees which will be resulting to increase in Individual and organizational productivity.

Limitation of the Study

- The usefulness of study is restricted to Mumbai region only
- The study is applicable to present scenario only.
- The study is made only on the youth working in corporate sector
- The study is generalized and indicative.

Research Methodology

A level of data collection always builds a strong base for good research work. This research is based on primary as well as secondary data. The Primary data is collected through survey method from Youth (22 to 35 years of Age) working in corporate sector. The purpose was to understand the problems arising during managing work and family life. The respondents were randomly selected from different corporate companies located in Mumbai. The sample size of research was kept 100 respondents. The collected data was analyzed using percentage method. Our survey method was an online questionnaire containing approx 35 questions. The participants are selected using samples of target population and the purpose.

The secondary data for the paper was collected from different Online Research Papers, Journals, Websites, and Articles.

Literature Review

The research work of Baral and Bhargava (2011) suggested that the Indian companies should be sensitized with the importance of implementing a well-planned and integrated work-life program. The organizations should encourage a culture which supports and promotes work life balance for improving employee commitment and productivity.

Madhurima Das and K B Akhilesh (2012) revealed in their research that work-life balance depends upon various variables like age, gender differences and occupational background of the employees.

Reimara Valk and Vasanthi Srinivasan (2011) highlighted in their research that work-life balance is influenced by six main variables like family influence on life related decisions or choices, multiple responsibilities which a person is expected to deal with, professional identity and perception of self, challenges in attaining a work-life balance and strategies for addressing the challenges, organizational procedures & policies and the support from the society.

A careful review of the literature on work-life balance indicates that work-life balance has got a strong association with the salary and age. It was also identified that work-life balance has a strong impact on the overall employee commitment towards their work and job satisfaction.

Data Analysis and Findings

Work-Life balance refers to an effective management or striking a balance between the work which is remunerated and the personal or social responsibilities which an individual is expected to perform. Work life can influence organizational

productivity and also the well being of the employees in different ways. Given below are some of the areas in terms of opportunities and concerns on which work life issues can have an impact:

1. **Impact on the Profitability and Growth:** Excessive pressure of achieving the profitability and growth targets builds stress, hampers the overall productivity of the employees and disturbs their work-life balance. A well planned and implemented work-life balance strategy may greatly ease the work pressure both on the job and perceived work pressures, which in turn will favorably propel employee productivity and contribute towards a positive return on investment.
2. **Employee Engagement at work and Quality of customer service:** An imbalance in the work and life front will adversely affect the complete engagement of the employees at work and hamper the quality of services delivered to the customers. On the other hand, the quality of service will be reliable and consistent; if the employees perceive that their efforts or their presence is valued by the management and also that the organization is committed to ensuring both personal and professional success of their employees.
3. **Talent Acquisition strategy and the Challenges related to it:** Increase in the composition of the baby boomers and relatively a young pool of working professionals, have increased their expectations for a favourable work life culture. They expect that apart from their work responsibilities they need to attend to the personal/social responsibilities of their life. In the present scenario, issues with work-life balance are considered to be the prime reasons for a high rate of employee turnover which definitely is an imposed cost on the organization. Research reveals that, Johnson & Johnson was able to achieve a reduction in the rate of absenteeism by almost 50% by introducing flexi-work options and employee welfare policies.
4. **Rising cost of Health Care & Medications:** Due to a rise in the level of work pressure and never ending expectations, a major percentage of the employees are faced with lifestyle related diseases and major health problems. This has become a serious issue of concern for the organizations because of the mounting cost of health care and drastic reduction in the ratio of employee productivity. Such concerns have compelled the management to pay importance to work-life balance priorities and creating a healthier workplace by implementing several developmental initiatives.

Work-life initiatives are not a choice but an imperative for the management in the present scenario. It is because, the employees look forward to the support and concern of the management towards their work-life related issues. HR today, holds the extra responsibility of implementing a gamut of initiatives for making their organization an attractive place to work for the employees.

Benefits of Healthy Work Life Balance

By understanding the importance of maintaining a healthy work-life balance, anyone will get motivated to take the necessary steps for achieving this balance. Work-Life balance is advantageous for the employees and organization as well. A balance between the work and personal life helps in improving the employee productivity, morale and health condition. In fact, work-life balance should be a priority for all of us. An imbalance in any of the front will make the life difficult and pose several hazards or challenges in terms of health, happiness and emotional stability.

The benefits of work-life balance are given below

- **Fulfilment:** People who maintain a balance between work and personal life experience a sense of fulfilment and contentment in their life.

- **Health:** A balanced work-life will help in reducing health related complications and the risk of various serious diseases of heart, hyper-tension, stress or life-style related ailments.
- **Improved Productivity:** Greater work-life balance will improve the employee productivity and performance at work.
- **Strengthen Relationship:** Work-life balance facilitates collaboration in professional and personal relationship. Conflicts are better tackled or addressed when there is a balance between both.

Following are the analyzed responses of respondents

Factor	Category	% of Respondents
Gender	Male	60
	Female	40
Age	20-25 Years	56
	26-30 Years	19
	31-35 Years	25
Work Experience	0-5 Years	81.6
	5-10 Years	17.5
	10-15 Years	1
Week Offs	Saturday, Sunday Off	43.7
	Second and Fourth Saturday Off	9.7
	No Fixed week offs	15.5
	Only Sunday off	31.1
Working Hours Per Week	Less than 30 Hours	13.6
	30 – 45 Hours	27.2
	45+ Hours	59.2
Does The Organization Take Initiatives To Manage Work Life Of Its Employees?	Yes	64.1
	No	35.9
Do you think policy for work Life Management helps to increase productivity of the organization?	Yes	65.3
	No	5
	May Be	29.7
Do you generally feel you are able to balance your work life due to work life management policy of the company?	Yes	58.3
	No	41.7
Have you missed a personal event because of work?	Yes	67
	No	33
Do you check emails on phone after you leave the office?	Yes	55.3
	No	44.7
How many hours do you sleep on an average work night?	Less than 5 hours	8.7
	5 – 8 Hours	71.8
	8 – 10 Hours	17.5
	More than 10 Hours	1.9

How often do you think or worry about work (when you are not actually at work or traveling to work)?

103 responses

Work Satisfaction

103 responses

Balance

103 responses

Stress

103 responses

How satisfied are you with your current work/life balance?

103 responses

Personal Life Satisfaction

103 responses

How often do you work on vacation?

103 responses

How often do you take work home?

103 responses

Are you satisfied with the working hours of the organization?

103 responses

The causes of work-life balance could be many such as tedious and long work hours, extra time invested in travelling, No sufficient Week offs. Work-life balance need not necessarily aim at achieving an equal balance. Giving same priority to every responsibility by way of proper scheduling and time management may practically be impossible, unrewarding and quite unrealistic too. Life should be more fluid and each step taken should be governed by the demands of the situation.

Suggestions

- Companies should provide trainings on time and stress management,
- 5days work policies can results positively in higher job satisfaction and higher level of productivity.
- No interaction should be made from office unless it's extremely important.
- There must be a standard working policy all over the nation
- Understanding of work priorities and Flexible working hours can play a major role in improvement of work life
- Companies should follow strict policies for personal times as well
- Every company should have separate panel or redreseel department regarding work life balance complaints or feedback
- Work culture should be design this way that after working hours no work should be allot or no calls for the same.
- Work should be evenly divided among team so that nobody does overtime. Enough resources should be provided for the same.
- Company should respect employees and their personal time
- Employees should avoid wastage of time in office and work effectively so that you do not need to work late at office.

Conclusion

The work-life balance has grown into much more than just an appealing concept. An increasing number of companies are relying on their employees to lead a more balanced lifestyle, as balanced, happy employees are ultimately more productive and motivated. If a company – either consciously or unconsciously – destroys an employee's private life with too much overtime or an unnatural amount of pressure, it will inevitably result in dissatisfaction and stress that can then lead to health problems, decreased productivity, and alienation from the company. The general dissatisfaction of employees worldwide signifies how far from achieving a work-life balance we really are. However, the working world is slowly changing as more and more companies are beginning to welcome the idea and are also specifically promoting it.

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